

Stress among Adolescents In Relation To School Environment

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Abstract

The present investigation focuses on the study of Stress among adolescents in relation to school environment. The survey method was adopted in this present study. In this study, 250 adolescents were taken as sample through the random sampling technique. The 't' test, ANOVA test, and Chi-square tests were used to analyse the data. The results revealed that the stress present among adolescents in school environment.

Key words: Stress, adolescents and school environment

Introduction

Adolescence means 'to emerge' to achieve 'identity'. Personhood is what we want the Adolescent to attain not only just in its physical or intellectual aspects but also in his/her whole human hood, which includes the often neglected but equally important aspects, which are emotional or psychological, social and spiritual. The time of growing up from childhood to adulthood is known as the Adolescence

The term "Adolescence" comes from the Latin word 'adolescere' that means "to grow" or "to grow to maturity". Maturing involves not only physical but also mental growth. It is a period, which fills the gap between childhood and adulthood. Generally, this period is termed as "youth". This period runs between childhood and adulthood, sometimes-called "the period of storm and stress". School environment is defined as a school having appropriate facilities, well-managed classrooms available school-based health supports, and a clear, fair disciplinary policy there are many hallmarks of the academic, disciplinary, and physical environments of schools with a positive climate.

Importance of Adolescents

1. An adolescent is a critical link between childhood and adulthood.
2. Characterised by significant physical, psychological and social transitions.
3. These transitions carry out risks but also present opportunities to positively influence the immediate and future health of young people.
4. While adolescent health is beginning to receive more attention at a global level.
5. These are still major gaps in both knowledge and action.

Need For The Study

Adolescents are a stressful period due to the physical, psychological and social changes. The pressure of psychiatric, anxiety and stress at the stage of life is a matter of concern. It is a time where a number of significant changes occur in a relatively

short period of time, and because some of these changes may be challenging for Adolescents. Students cannot make rational or tell the difference between right and wrong it means they should not be held responsible for their action.

Since they are falling in many social activities like suicide, conflict, frustration and minor and major crime. The knowledge of various stress is very essential for the Adolescents student to understand the day today problems that they are facing routinely. In order to resolved and cope up the above knowledge are mandatory for the learners. This study is helpful to reduce the stress of adolescents in school environment and plan appropriate counselling technique to provide to those who are in need. This study is also useful to prevent Adolescents learner's rate of suicidal attempts.

Objectives of The Study

1. To find out the difference in the stress among Adolescents in relation to school environment based on their gender.
2. To find out the difference in the stress among Adolescents in relation to school environment based on their medium of instruction.
3. To find out the difference in the stress among Adolescents in relation to school environment based on their locality of school
4. To find out the difference in the stress among Adolescents in relation to school environment based on their type of family.
5. To find out the difference in the stress among Adolescents in relation to school environment based on their type of school.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between male and female adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.
2. There is no significant difference between Tamil medium and English medium adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.

3. There is no significant difference between rural and urban adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.
4. There is no significant difference between adolescents belonging to joint family and nuclear family in their stress in relation to school environment.
5. There is no significant difference among adolescents studying in Government, government aided and private school in their stress in relation to school environment

Method for the Study

In the present study, research is conducted in the survey method and on the basis of that interferences are drawn about whole populations. According to Webster's Collegiate Dictionary, Survey is a critical inspection, often official to provide exact information, a study of an area with respect to a certain condition or its prevalence, Survey method helps the investigator to collect more information from very large samples.

Population of the Study

The second part which is used to ascertain the characteristics of the large group is called

sample. Alternatively, sample is a subsection or cross section of the large group. The large group from which a sample is selected for any research project is known as population. All possible units or elements that make up a large group make up the population. The population for the present study consists of stress among adolescents in relation to school environment in Coimbatore district.

Samples for the Study

The investigator adopted simple random sampling technique, for collecting the sample for the study. A sample of 250 students from types of managements namely Government, Government Aided, and private schools are selected by the investigator for the present study.

Tools Used In the Study

Construction of tool is another important step in a research study. The tool was developed and validated by the investigator

Data Analysis

Null hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.

TABLE: 1 Stress Among Adolescents In Relation To School Environment: Gender

Gender	Number of sample	Mean	SD	Calculated t- value	Table value At 5%level	Remarks At 5% level
Male	129	69.33	6.495	5.131	1.96	Significant
Female	121	73.55	6.503			

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated 't' value 5.131 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. The mean score of female students (73.55) is higher than the male students (69.33). So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant difference

between male and female adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.

Null hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between Tamil medium and English medium adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.

TABLE : 2 Stress Among Adolescents In Relation To School Environment: Medium Of Instruction

Medium of instruction	Number of sample	Mean	SD	calculated t- value	Table value at 5%level	Remarks at 5% level
TAMIL	184	71.86	6.721	1.931	1.96	Not significant
ENGLISH	66	69.98	6.958			

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated 't' value 1.931 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance, the mean score of Tamil medium students is 71.86. higher than English medium students is 69.98. So the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no significant difference between Tamil medium and English

medium adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment

Null hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between rural and urban adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.

TABLE: 3 Stress Among Adolescents In Relation To School Environment: Locality Of School

Locality of School	Number of sample	Mean	SD	Calculated t- value	Table value at 5%level	Remarks at 5% level
RURAL	43	70.63	7.509	0.781	1.96	Not Significant
URBAN	207	71.52	6.679			

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated 't'-value 0.781 is lower than that of the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. The mean score of rural school students is 70.63 and urban school students is 71.52. which shows that there is a slight difference in their mean scores. So the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no significant difference between rural and

urban adolescents in their stress in relation to school environment.

Null hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between adolescents belonging to joint family and nuclear family in their stress in relation to school environment.

TABLE 4 Stress Among Adolescents In Relation To School Environment: Type Of Family

Type of Family	Number of sample	Mean	SD	Calculated t- value	Table value at 5% level	Remarks
FAMILY JOINT	37	69.22	8.284	2.093	1.96	Significant
NUCLEAR FAMILY	213	71.74	6.485			

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated 't'-value 2.093 is higher than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Mean score of nuclear family is (71.74) higher than the joint family (69.22) So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant difference between adolescents belonging to joint family and nuclear

family in their stress in relation to school environment.

Null hypothesis 5

Null Hypotheses – 5

There is no significant difference among adolescents studying in Government, government aided and private school in their stress in relation to school environment.

TABLE 5 (a): Stress Among Adolescents In Relation To School Environment: Type Of School - Anova Test

Type of School	Number of sample	Mean	SD
Government	116	71.43	6.420
Govt. aided	44	68.25	6.989
Private	90	72.81	6.812

From the above table, it is observed that, there is difference in the mean value of stress among adolescents in relation to school environment in the scores among government, govt. aided and private school students. Private school students are higher

than the mean score of government and govt. Aided school students.

In order to find out whether there is significance difference in mean scores, F- test was applied to the following table that gives the result of F- test with reference to the type of school.

Table 5 (b) Anova Test: Type of School

Source of variance	Sum squares	df	MS	Calculated F- value	Table value at 5% level	Remarks
Between groups	615.657	2	307.828	6.931	3.00	Significant
Within groups	10970.487	247	44.415			

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated F- value is 6.931 higher than the table value 3.00 at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hence there is a significant difference among adolescents studying in Government, government aided and private school in their stress in relation to school environment.

Recommendations

Students are the wealth and future of a nation. It is clear from the findings that male and female participants have more academic stress participants. Their academic problem must be discussed by the

teacher as well as parents. And they must be guided properly to choose a specific stream, not forced by parents. Parents should have expectations by their children according their capability. This study recommended that the teacher should arrange the necessary healthy environment to reduce the students' academic stress. The teachers' should focus on reducing the students' academic stress by providing mentors classes, time scheduling activities, changing teaching method, and providing extracurricular activities.

Conclusion

School staff should make schools a safe place where there are fewer chances that students have to make difficult decisions. Classrooms need to be safe havens. When students have any doubt that they can be successful doing an assignment or task, the stress response goes into motion. Students need to know that the teacher is on their side and will give them many opportunities to learn. Parents should encourage their children to learn respectful behaviour by thinking before he or she speaks to. Parents should encourage their children to participate in exercise and physical activities. Join in to model fitness. The result of this study may help school staffs, teachers and counsellors to understand why some students display high anxiety, fear, and depression. The focus of intervention programs should be on training students to have a healthy mind set with positive coping strategies. Parents and teachers should provide activities for the students which help them to enjoy their free time, including exercise, and allow them sometime to be completely unproductive for reducing stress. School staffs, teachers and counsellors should develop ways to improve effective communication between students and teachers, thereby improving academic and social efficiency of students. Their understanding of students' academic stress will help them to practice techniques and adopt essential to assist and mentor them to cope/deal with academic stress more effective.

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